

The following artifacts are submitted to support the commitments made in the Open Science section of our paper:

1. **Interview Recruitment Messages** – Includes the text used for participant recruitment in the interview study.
2. **Consent Form** – We used the version available at the time of the study, in accordance with the University's data protection policy, and submitted the important details for your reference.
3. **Demographics Questionnaire** – Questions related to the participants' background information and UPI experience are provided.
4. **Interview Guide and Script (English, Hindi, Telugu)** – To support the reproducibility of our study we added all three language versions of the interview guide (the English version is added in Appendix A of the paper)
5. **Interview Codebook** – It outlines the coding structure used to analyze the interview data and is added in Appendix C of the paper
6. **Advice Codebook** – It provides the coding structure of security advice from official UPI entities, banks, and regulatory bodies.